

Basseri

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Iranian Religion, Islamic Traditions, Shiite/Shi'a

The Basseri are a society of nomadic pastoralists in the Fars Province of Iran who distinguish themselves from their diverse neighbors through primarily political allegiance (as opposed to distinct cultural features or language) (Adem, 2009:1). This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence collected during fieldwork with the Basseri in 1958, during which time the political leader of the Basseri was still recognized by the Iranian government and the Basseri were largely autonomous. However, immediately after this time period, the Basseri chief was dismissed from power, with the Iranian Army assuming power over the Basseri instead. The Basseri identify themselves as Shia Muslims. However, during the time focus of this entry, religion and religious practices were not a very significant part of everyday life. Prayer was irregular, and observance of annual Islamic festivals was minimal. Most ceremonies, even if invoking some religious elements, were oriented more toward major life events rather than religion. While explicit religious practice was not strictly adhered to, it appears that religious beliefs were still inseparable from most aspects of social and political life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1943 CE - 1958 CE

Region: Nomadic branch, ca. 1958

Region tags: Iran

Nomadic branch of the Basseri, Fars Province, Iran, ca. 1958

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. *Ethnographic Atlas*. *Ethnology* 1-10.
- Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11(3): 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma10-000>
- Source 1 Description: Adem, Teferi Abate. 2009. "Culture Summary: Basseri." New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma10-001>

–Source 2 Description: Barth, Fredrik. 1961. "Nomads of South-Persia: The Basseri Tribe of the Khamseh Confederacy." In *Bulletin*, x, 159. Oslo: University Press; Humanities Press.

–Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma10-002>

–Source 3 Description: Barth, Fredrik. 1969. "Capital, Investment and the Social Structure of a Pastoral Nomad Group in South Persia." In *Capital, Saving and Credit in Peasant Societies: Studies from Asia, Oceania, the Caribbean and Middle America*, 69–81, 387–93. Chicago: Aldine Publishing Co.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, political and religious leaders are distinct (Ross, 1983; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, ethnographic evidence indicates that religious leaders are not present: "There are no ritual officers of any kind in the tribe . . ." (Barth, 1961:136).

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Basseri do not enforce religious observance: "The Basseri, as Shiah [Muslims], accept the general premises and proscriptions of Islam to the extent that they are familiar with them. On the other hand, they are aware of their own laxity in these matters, and are generally uninterested in religion as preached by Persian mullahs, and indifferent to metaphysical problems" (Barth, 1961:135).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16000

Notes: "Today [the population] is estimated at nearly 3,000 tents, or roughly 16,000 inhabitants" (Barth, 1961:1).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "There are no ritual officers of any kind in the tribe . . ." (Barth, 1961:136).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "A literate or quasi-literate person tries to chant the appropriate texts from the Koran . . ." (Barth, 1961:143).

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: "A literate or quasi-literate person tries to chant the appropriate texts from the Koran . . ." (Barth, 1961:143).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972:259,268; note: equivalent to SCCS variable 66).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that cemeteries are present: "The corpse is buried within a day of death; for this purpose it is always carried to a village cemetery, never buried out in the hills; prominent men are sometimes brought to the closest shrine for burial" (Barth, 1961:142).

Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse is buried within a day of death; for this purpose it is always carried to a

village cemetery, never buried out in the hills; prominent men are sometimes brought to the closest shrine for burial" (Barth, 1961:142).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "In the course of such a cycle [the annual migration cycle], the nomad passes by a succession of localities, and many points along the way are marked with shrines (Imamzadeh/Ziarat) in the form of the graves of holy men" (Barth, 1961:137).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse is buried within a day of death; for this purpose it is always carried to a village cemetery, never buried out in the hills; prominent men are sometimes brought to the closest shrine for burial" (Barth, 1961:142).

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse is buried within a day of death; for this purpose it is always carried to a village cemetery, never buried out in the hills; prominent men are sometimes brought to the closest shrine for burial" (Barth, 1961:142).

Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse is buried within a day of death; for this purpose it is always carried to a village cemetery, never buried out in the hills; prominent men are sometimes brought to the closest shrine for burial" (Barth, 1961:142).

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "The corpse is buried within a day of death; for this purpose it is always carried to a village cemetery, never buried out in the hills; prominent men are sometimes brought to the closest shrine for burial" (Barth, 1961:142).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "Present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34). However, ethnographic evidence regarding supernatural beings is unavailable for the time and place focus of this entry.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: While SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, indicates that a supreme high god is "Present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34), no ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– I don't know

Notes: The Basseri hold primarily Islamic religious beliefs, and in Islam, messianic beliefs are present. Thus, it is assumed that messianic beliefs are present among the Basseri. However, no ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of messianic beliefs.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In connection with joyful events or particular successes, e. g. in hunting, a person is expected to give sweets to the members of his community. This is explained as an effort to prevent envy and evil eye, and to express a feeling of friendship and good will towards all" (Barth, 1961:145).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Basseri highly value hospitality and moderation of consumption. See questions below for details.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: "The basic guiding principle which they adopt comes out in an almost obsessive desire to postpone every incident of consumption . . ." (Barth, 1969:79).

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Hospitality

Notes: ". . . hospitality is a highly valued virtue" (Barth, 1969:79).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sex restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sex restrictions.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "Every day for the first three days of its life, and every subsequent Wednesday (Charshambe) for 40 days, the infant is cut on nose, neck and chest with razor blades, later also on the ears. This is to prevent the child's blood from becoming unclean later in life . . ." (Barth, 1961:138).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: "Each household which is represented [at a shrine to Said Mohammed] should give an animal in sacrifice by the shrine – though often several tents combine for a single sacrifice, to save animals" (Barth, 1961:137).

Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: "Each household which is represented [at a shrine to Said Mohammed] should give an animal in sacrifice by the shrine – though often several tents combine for a single sacrifice, to save animals" (Barth, 1961:137).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that sacrifice of time is not required: "The nomads pray irregularly and always individually; even on Friday there is no communal gathering of worshippers within a camp or even within a tent" (Barth, 1961:136).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: "Only few references have been made to ritual in this account of the Basseri – hardly any ceremonies have been described, and the behaviour patterns have been discussed in terms of the pragmatic systems of economics, or politics, and hardly ever in terms of their meanings within a ritual system" (Barth, 1961:135).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: "Only few references have been made to ritual in this account of the Basseri – hardly any ceremonies have been described, and the behaviour patterns have been discussed in terms of the pragmatic systems of economics, or politics, and hardly ever in terms of their meanings within a ritual system" (Barth, 1961:135).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scarring, circumcision, and traditional hairstyles. See questions below for details.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "Every day for the first three days of its life, and every subsequent Wednesday (Charshambe) for 40 days, the infant is cut on nose, neck and chest with razor blades, later also on the ears" (Barth, 1961:138).

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: "Boys are circumcised, generally by a village barber or physician, before the age of two months" (Barth, 1961:138).

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: "Married status is often, though not always, marked by women by a change of hair style, whereby the hair is cut short and bobbed, instead of leaving it long and loosely tucked under the headcloth, in the fashion of unmarried girls" (Barth, 1961:142).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, the Basseri had two levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a tribe (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that famine was generally not present: "Famines, on the other hand, never seem to have been a major direct threat, though periods of want may have had their effect in reducing the natural resistance of the tribesmen to disease" (Barth, 1961:108).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: "Serious loss of wealth in a household thus has the result that the household is sloughed off from the tribe; or, to put it the other way around, the persistence of the present form of Basseri organization depends on a continual process of sloughing-off of members who fail to retain the productive capital in herds which is required for an independent pastoral existence" (Barth, 1961:108).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: "The chief must deal with all of them, without offending any: with the local commanding General and the Headquarters in Teheran; with representatives in Parliament and with the secretariat for tribal affairs at the Shah's court; with the Provincial Governor, the legal courts, and so on . . ." (Barth, 1961:96).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: "[Agriculture] is under these conditions [in southern Iranian climate] almost completely dependent on artificial irrigation. Water is drawn by channels from natural rivers and streams in the area, or, by the help of various contraptions, raised by animal traction from wells, particularly by oxen and horses" (Barth, 1961:4).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: "The ruling chief has the recognized right to impose irregular taxes on the tribesmen, usually in the form of a tax of one sheep in a hundred (sad-o-yek) or sometimes even as much as three sheep in

hundred (sad-o-seh)" (Barth, 1961:74).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions among the Basseri are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "In the small and closely knit communities that constitute camps, most matters of law are governed by custom and compromise and regulated by diffuse sanctions. Where disputes cannot be settled informally, recourse may be had to the chief, who alone constitutes the only 'court' in the tribal system" (Barth, 1961:77).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The Colonel [of the Iranian Army overseeing the Basseri], like the chief before him, mediates in the solution of conflicts when tribesmen are called before civil courts" (Barth, 1961:96).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "In the small and closely knit communities that constitute camps, most matters of law are governed by custom and compromise and regulated by diffuse sanctions. Where disputes cannot be settled informally, recourse may be had to the chief, who alone constitutes the only 'court' in the tribal system" (Barth, 1961:77).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "In the small and closely knit communities that constitute camps, most matters of law are governed by custom and compromise and regulated by diffuse sanctions. Where disputes cannot be settled informally, recourse may be had to the chief, who alone constitutes the only 'court' in the tribal system" (Barth, 1961:77).

Warfare

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The distinction between these two categories [formally recognized chief and informal headman] has broken down somewhat since the Iranian Army assumed administrative control over the tribe two years ago, because of the practice of the administering Colonel to elevate all camp leaders to the status of formally recognized headmen" (Barth, 1961:26).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, the Basseri possess true writing but no records (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The Basseri operate in a sense within three separate calendrical systems: the Islamic year, the Persian or solar year, and the yearly cycle of their own migrations, which brings them past the same series of localities in a regular succession." (Barth, 1961:136).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The Basseri operate in a sense within three separate calendrical systems: the Islamic year, the Persian or solar year, and the yearly cycle of their own migrations, which brings them past the same series of localities in a regular succession." (Barth, 1961:136).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for themselves. The Basseri depend primarily on pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) and small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation) as secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Basseri depend primarily on pastoralism (SCCS Variable 206, Dependence on Animal Husbandry), with hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) and small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation) as secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).